

Assessing the Employment Situation of Students after Graduating From the Dien Bien College of Economics and Technology

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Abstract:

This report aims to assess the employment situation of students after graduating from the Dien Bien College of Economics and Technology from 2011 to 2017. The author approached and surveyed a total of 312/878 Alumni, the result of the total number of graduates surveyed is 312. The percentage of graduates who have employed 193 is 62.1%; The rate of unemployed students is 37.9%. In which, the rate of students having jobs in the right field is 119, reaching 61.7%. Of the four sectors surveyed, the Accounting sector has the highest percentage of graduates with jobs (73.0%), the Banking and Finance sector has the lowest rate (55.5%), and the Livestock sector. raising the rate of graduates with employed jobs ranked second (62.3%), and the Crop Science sector reached 62.1%. In which, the rate of students having the highest job in the livestock sector is the highest (100%), the accounting sector is 66.3%, the science of plantation reaches 60.0%, the banking and finance sector reaches 47, 5%.

Keywords: Assessment, employment.

1. Introduction

Over the past years, Dien Bien College of Economics and Engineering has paid attention to the opinions of related parties, especially customers and has conducted a number of surveys: Feedback of learners about activities teaching activities of Lecturers; survey the satisfaction level of students on the module; Poll of graduates and employers about the training quality of the school. However, the situation of the employment situation and the level of meeting employers' needs after The school has not been implemented yet. Statistical data on the employment situation of post-graduate students and the response level of employers' needs are considered useful information to help the school improve the training program thereby improving quality. Amount of training. From those reasons, I selected the study "Assessing the employment situation of students after graduating from the Dien Bien College of Economics and Technology".

2. Some concepts related to research

2.1. Employment

Employment or work is an activity that is frequently performed in exchange for payment of wages, usually a person's occupation. A person often starts a job by becoming an employee, volunteer, or starting a business. The time limit for a job can range from one hour (in the case of odd jobs) or a lifetime (in the case of judges). If a person is trained for a certain type of job, they may have a career. A series of jobs for a person in their lifetime is their career. A job must have a beginning and an end, a goal, a result, a resource.

2.2. Evaluate

In the field of education, there are many different definitions of assessment. However, it still depends much on the level of assessment, on the target, the purpose to be assessed. According to the author Lam Quang Thiep, the assessment is based on measurements and criteria to determine the capacity and quality of training products to identify, judge and propose decisions to improve stop training quality. Evaluation can be quantitatively based on numbers or qualitative based on opinions and values.

In education, the assessment is understood: "is the process of forming judgments and judgments about the results of the work, based on the analysis of the obtained information, comparing with the goals and criteria In order to propose appropriate decisions to improve the situation, adjust the quality and efficiency of the work ". According to author J.M. Deketele, "Evaluation means considering the appropriateness of a set of information obtained with a set of relevant criteria of a defined goal in order to make a decision on a certain purpose. Assessment, according to author Nguyen Trong Phuc, can be understood as "the process of determining the level of achieving the goal of teaching purposes, is a qualitative and quantitative description of the aspects of knowledge, skills, and ergonomics. students' degrees compare

with the targets of the intended purpose and desire of the subject ”. According to Pham Xuan Thanh's price tag in the series on assessment theory: "Evaluation is a general term for systematically collecting information and processing and analyzing data as a basis for giving making decisions to improve the quality of education ”Assessment is the ability to assess the value of data (speeches, poetry, novels, research reports, etc.) according to a given list. This assessment is based on clear criteria. These criteria may be internal criteria (organization) or external criteria (related to purpose). Students can identify criteria or be given those criteria. In the list of technical terms, evaluation is a process that includes measurement and testing, can also include concepts related to valuable decisions. If the teacher manages a science test for a class and calculates the percentage of scores received then the measurement and evaluation are one. In this case, scores are converted into values such as A, B, C, D ... understood as: great, good, normal and poor. This is considered a valuable evaluation process. Evaluation is sometimes based only on objective data. However, more common is still the process of synthesizing from many sources of information such as scores, values or impressions from the test. In any event, the evaluation also includes making valuable decisions. Although there are many different definitions of assessment, all of them generally consider evaluation as the process of considering the appropriateness between the goal and the actual implementation of that goal. In other words, the assessment is concerned with the correlation between specific information on the status of education and the educational goals, thereby taking appropriate measures to improve the efficiency and quality of education and training.

3. Research methods

The study organized a survey of 312/878 alumni who graduated from 2011 - 2017 through a questionnaire. The total number of training industries surveyed includes 4 colleges of 2 Faculties:

- + Banking and Finance, Accounting (Faculty of Economics - Finance).
- + Science plants, Livestock (Faculty of Science - Engineering)

The questionnaire consists of 7 questions about the status of graduates' jobs. In addition, the questionnaire has 2 questions related to solutions to improve the quality of school training.

4. Research results

4.1. Assessment of training activities of Dien Bien College of Economics and Technology

* Advantage Dien Bien College of Economics - Engineering is currently training 07 college-level majors; 12 professional intermediate level professions, 10 elementary level professions, 20 regular training professions. In addition, the University is also associated with 11 universities and colleges associated with training from Professional Intermediate, College to University; University degree 2; University of both working and studying forms. From 2011 - 2017, the University has organized a Master's degree training at the school for the provincial cadres and civil servants. From the school year 2008 - 2009, the school began to train the College. Up to now (April 15, 2018), there have been 7 courses of graduating from college. The total number of students graduating from the school is 787 students, specifically each branch as follows:

Table 01: Statistics of the number of students graduating from university (from 2011 to 2017)

TT	majors	Graduation year							Total
		2011	2012	2013	2014	2015	2016	2017	
		course 1	course 2	course 3	course 4	course 5	course 6	course 7	
1	Banking and Finance	52	52	69	58	42	20	10	303
2	Accounting	67	64	47	122	49	22	14	385
3	Crop Science	0	11	17	11	7	16	10	72
4	Breed	0	0	9	4	5	9	0	27
	Total	119	127	142	195	103	67	34	787

(Data source: Training Department - Career, Employment Consultancy)

In general, most of the students have a sense of learning, training, and cultivation; having a sense of striving to rise up, having a spirit of solidarity and mutual assistance, it is shown in the high learning and training results. Every year (from 2008 - 2017), the rate of students grading and studying from average to above is over 80%. The number of students with moderate and weak learning and training ranks very little.

In order to ensure the quality of training, in parallel with the expansion of branches and training scale, the school has paid attention to the construction and development of the team. To date, the total number of school officials and employees is 139 people. In which, 104 teachers (accounting for 73.2%); Doctoral level: 02 people (accounting for 1.9% of the total number of lecturers); Master: 72 people (accounting for 69.2% of the total number of lecturers); Currently, the school has 07 cadres and lecturers studying domestic and foreign students. Officers, lecturers, and staff are rejuvenated, have strong political qualities, dynamic and creative in their work, always uphold the spirit of solidarity, mutual affection, overcome difficulties to complete the mission service.

The facilities and technical equipment of the school have been invested and upgraded, contributing significantly to the effective implementation of the school's training.

With the mission of building a modern and human cultural environment in the knowledge economy, creating opportunities for learners to learn for life. Application of scientific and technological achievements in teaching and learning. Providing advanced educational services in the fields of economy, technology, social culture, ensuring the sustainable development of the school and society, implementing the goal "Prestige - Quality - Responsibility social responsibility ". The school pays special attention to quality assurance, from the school year 2012-2013, the school has applied the quality management system ISO 9001: 2008 to the quality management of education and training, annually the school set a quality policy and a quality goal, which pays attention to the survey of graduates and employers on the employment situation and the quality of education and training of the school.

*Hard

Some cadres and teachers have a young age, and their working experience is lacking; The number of teachers with deep expertise is low. The material and technical facilities for training, teaching and learning facilities of the school have been paid attention to by the province, but the investment is still lacking and inconsistent, failing to meet the development requirements with scale and industry. vocational training is increasingly expanding; rooms for accounting practice, informatics practice and text drafting and library houses are still lacking. The rate of students achieving good and good academic performance in recent years accounts for a low proportion: 12.4% in the academic year 2012-2013; in the academic year 2013 - 2014 accounted for 22.1%, the school year 2014 - 2015 accounted for 15, 1%; the school year 2015 - 2016 accounted for 24.1%; 2016-2017 academic year accounted for 19.6%. The payroll closure in recent years has affected the opportunity to find jobs for students after graduation.

4.2. Assessing the situation of post-graduation employment of students at Dien Bien College of Economics and Technology.

Table 02: Statistics of votes issued and collected

N ₀	Majors	Employer (1)			Students have graduated (2)			Total (1+2)		
		Number of votes issued	Number of votes collected	Ratio %	Number of votes issued	Number of votes collected	Ratio %	Number of votes issued	Number of votes collected	Ratio %
1	Banking and Finance	30	30	100	110	110	100	140	140	100
2	Accounting	59	59	100	131	131	100	190	190	100
3	Crop Science	15	15	100	52	52	100	67	67	100
4	Breed	12	12	100	19	19	100	31	31	100
5	Total	116	116	100	312	312	100	428	428	100

Table 03: Statistics on the employment status of students after graduation (from 2011 to 2017)

N ₀	Majors	Total number of students surveyed	Number of students without jobs		Number of students with jobs		Number of students having jobs in the right field		Average salary/month
			Amount	Ratio %	Amount	Ratio %	Amount	Ratio %	
1	Banking and Finance	110	49	44,5	61	55,5	29	47,5	5 triệu
2	Accounting	131	36	27,0	95	73,0	63	66,3	6 triệu
3	Crop Science	52	27	51,9	25	48,1	15	60,0	4 triệu
4	Breed	19	7	36,8	12	63,2	12	100	4,5 triệu
5	Total	312	118	37,9	193	62,1	119	61,7	

Through table 03, we see that the total number of graduates surveyed is 312. The percentage of graduates who have employed 193 is 62.1%; The rate of unemployed students is 37.9%. In which, the rate of students having jobs in the right field is 119, reaching 61.7%. Although the survey has not been conducted for all graduates, the above results show that, in the context of economic and social changes, especially the closure of staff in recent years, the birth rate Graduates who have a job of the school still have a quite good rate, in which the majority have jobs in the right field, the income level ensures family life.

Of the four sectors surveyed, the Accounting sector has the highest percentage of graduates with jobs (73.0%), the Banking and Finance sector has the lowest rate (55.5%), and the Livestock sector. raising the rate of graduates with employed jobs ranked second (62.3%), and the Crop Science sector reached 62.1%. In which, the rate of students having the highest job in the livestock sector is the highest (100%), the accounting sector is 66.3%, the science of plantation reaches 60.0%, the banking and finance sector reaches 47, 5%.

4.3. Proposing a number of measures to improve the quality of education and training to meet the social needs of the school.

* Periodically improve the training program

The school periodically reviews and improves the training program, in which it is necessary to consider and refer to the results of employers' surveys on the quality of education and training of the school, ensuring the scientific and design characteristics. Redundancy of current training programs:

+ Demonstrating the training objectives of the corresponding qualifications; regulating the standard of knowledge and skills of learners after graduation; scope and structure of content, methods, and forms of training; how to assess learning results for each module, subject, each discipline, each level as prescribed.

+ Participation of teachers, professional education managers, scientific and technical staff of employers;

+ Ensuring practicality, meeting the changes of the labor market;

+ There is an update of advanced scientific and technological achievements related to training disciplines or reference of equivalent foreign training programs;

+ Ensure the connection between the levels of vocational education with other qualifications in the national education system according to regulations.

* Focus on learning service

The school should focus on investing in equipment for practice and experiments of students, in order to meet the requirements of the training program, contributing to improving the quality of vocational education.

* Periodically take opinions of graduated learners and labor recruitment agencies

Annually, the school organizes a survey of graduates and employers in order to consult and evaluate the training quality of the school, thereby serving as a basis for chapter improvement. training program to meet social needs.

When surveying, it is necessary to attach importance to the design of scientific questionnaires, organize appropriate ballot papers and handle accurate data in order to obtain high-value results.

5. Conclusion

The study organized a survey of 312 graduates on employment after graduation: The percentage of graduates who have employed 193 reached 62.1%; the rate of unemployed students is 37.9%. In which, the rate of students having jobs in the right field is 119, reaching 61.7%. Of the four sectors surveyed, the Accounting sector has the highest percentage of graduates with jobs (73.0%), the Banking and Finance sector has the lowest rate (55.5%), and the Livestock sector. raising the rate of graduates with employed jobs ranked second (62.3%), and the Crop Science sector reached 62.1%. In which, the rate of students having the highest job in the livestock sector is the highest (100%), the accounting sector is 66.3%, the science of plantation reaches 60.0%, the banking and finance sector reaches 47, 5%.

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